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Exploring the Psychosocial Experiences and Mental Health Support of First-Generation Working College Students

Darwin F. Ignacio, MA, Rpm, RGC

Guidance Counselor and Psychology Instructor

Notre Dame of Dadiangas University

Region 12

ABSTRACT

Dealing with work, academic, and personal demands is difficult for first-generation working college students. They are the first in their families to enter college, and they hold down jobs to support their educational expenses. Along their college journey, their mental health becomes at stake. This situation led the study to explore the psychosocial experiences they encountered and their sources of mental health support in a qualitative-phenomenological research design. Eight participants who fit the study's requirements were selected through purposeful sampling and engaged in semi-structured interviews. The thematic analysis proposed by Braun and Clarke was used to analyze and interpret the data collected from the interviews. Results revealed six themes describing their psychosocial experiences: coping with stress, limited socialization, adjusting to the work environment, managing time effectively, facing academic difficulties, and dealing with family issues. Further, five themes were drawn out describing the sources of their mental health support: self-reliance, family, friends, guidance from professionals, and learning from books. The findings implied the need to implement intensive intervention programs that address their present concerns.

Keywords: first-generation college students, working students, psychosocial experiences, mental health support, phenomenology, implications, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

A first-generation college student is the first member of their family to earn a degree from college. To support their quest for higher education, some of them need to render work, which several studies have accounted for this phenomenon across the globe (Astudillo et al.,

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2019; Cheng & Alcántara, 2007; Giray, 2022; Ives & Castillo-Montoya, 2020; Ma et al., 2021). Also, as they pursue their college dreams, these students must overcome several obstacles, such as time management, attending and setting priorities, and maintaining academic performance (Coral, 2020; Pedroso et al., 2022; Tumin, 2020). Further, their quality of life has been at risk due to the challenging aspects of being working students (Graves et al., 2017; Jaavall, 2007; Vernet, 2019). With this, they must endure whatever comes their way to achieve their educational goals.

As they proceed through college, their psychosocial experiences become overwhelming, leading to the point that their mental health becomes at stake. Various studies found that they are vulnerable to depression, stress, and anxiety (Khawar et al., 2021; Lim et al., 2022; Malolos et al., 2021; Serrano & Reyes, 2022). A recent study by Casamorin et al. (2023) found that working students are susceptible to suicidal risks. In addition, they have to juggle personal, work, and academic demands, which is a great challenge for them (Rockman, 2021; Tumin et al., 2020; Zhang, 2019). Therefore, if they do not handle their psychosocial experiences appropriately, it might negatively influence their work-life balance.

The students have yet to become accustomed to using mental health services which are vital to consider whenever they experience mental health concerns. In the helping field, mental health support may come from local or external help that enhances psychosocial well-being and prevents or treats mental diseases (UNHCR | Emergency Handbook, n.d.). These supports safeguard their psychological states while addressing their emotional needs and other pressing concerns. For instance, they can avail the counseling service of their schools, engage in psychoeducational activities, and go to psychological or psychiatric clinics, which all help address whatever mental health issues they face (Arnado & Bayod, 2020; Dela Cruz et al., 2023; Lattie et al., 2019). Therefore, mental health supports are positive interventions to ensure they earn their college degrees without jeopardizing their well-being.

In the locale context, the number of working students is increasing. According to the reports collated by the Department of Labor and Employment - Region XII, in 2022, there were 8,961 students registered for Special Employment for Working Students or SPES (DOLE Regional Office No. XII, n.d.). As their population grows, the prevalence of them having mental health concerns is also rising (Abenoja et al., 2019). Further, various studies conducted in the Philippines have explored their lived experiences which accounted for the state of their well-being (Arnado et al., 2020; Casamorin et al., 2023; Paje, 2023). Thus, becoming a working student is challenging; yet, many still choose that path. They must work hard to transcend their status quo despite whatever experiences they encounter.

It is necessary to explore the psychosocial experiences of first-generation working college students. The psychosocial adjustments, quality of life, challenging experiences, and

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current state of their well-being are critical factors in understanding some parts of their experiences. Also, it is vital to explore their mental health supports as they cope with their psychosocial experiences. They strive to make their dreams materialize not just for them but also for their family. They must sacrifice a lot to build their path to earning college degrees. Along the road, they will face various experiences that may endanger their mental state. As the study sets its aims, it may give valuable insights to stakeholders and mental health service providers to improve, enhance, or create programs for intervention.

Research Questions

This study explored the experiences of first-generation working college students enrolled in selected higher-educational institutions in General Santos City. Specifically, it sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What psychosocial experiences do first-generation working college students encounter?
2. What are their sources of mental health support?

METHOD

This section describes the research design, selection of the participants, research instrument, data gathering procedure, data analysis, ethical considerations, and rigors of qualitative research.

Research Design

Employing a qualitative-phenomenological research design helped answer the study's objectives. According to Tenny et al. (2017), qualitative research design looks at actual issues and offers a more in-depth understanding as it collects people's experiences, viewpoints, and actions. In addition, Creswell (2012) described the phenomenological approach as a systematic subjective strategy used to describe life events and provide a complete picture of a subject from the viewpoint of the investigated people. It fundamentally focuses on the participants' lived experiences and seeks to understand how and why people acted in a given way from their perspective.

The qualitative-phenomenological research design is most appropriate for this research endeavor because the present study expanded and deepened the understanding of the participant's experiences. In this study, the participants were first-generation working college students. At the same time, the investigated phenomena are their psychosocial

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experiences, which include the adjustments and challenges they encounter, and their overall quality of life. Also, the study explored the mental health supports they utilize in handling their experiences.

Selection of the Participants

In qualitative research, purposeful sampling is frequently used to find and choose information-rich instances connected to the phenomenon of interest (Creswell, 2012; Palinkas et al., 2015). In the present study, the researcher applied this sampling technique to determine the criteria and the number of participants. The study explored the experiences of eight chosen participants who met the criteria described below.

The selected participants must be first-generation working college students. It means that they are the first members of their family to enter college, and they are also working students. In addition, they must be enrolled in selected higher educational institutions in General Santos City, specifically at Notre Dame of Dadiangas University and Cronasia Foundation College.

The study does not limit the participants according to their sex, assigned work offices, courses, and year level. However, this study excluded participants working outside General Santos City, those who are self-employed, or those who render work for four years or more.

Research Instrument

The study used semi-structured interviews. According to Busetto et al. (2020), it is one of the data collection methods that allows researchers to gather information by asking open-ended questions. In this study, there were a total of eight interview questions seeking to uncover first-generation working college students' experiences. In addition, the interview guide composed four open-ended questions to describe participants' psychosocial experiences and another four open-ended questions to determine the mental health supports they utilize. The interview guide underwent a validation process. Three research experts validated the tool to ensure the interview questions align with the study's objectives. The researcher conducted pilot interviews before the study's actual conduct to test the interview questions' understandability.

Data Gathering Procedure

This study's execution included several steps. These included the selection of the participants who would fit the requirements, the conduct of semi-structured interviews, data

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processing, and interpretation, as Creswell (2012) and Ignacio (2023) suggested. First, a pre-survey was performed to find potential participants from the research location. Then, the criteria were established for the selection of participants. Next, an interview guide was developed to fully explore the participants' experiences in light of the study's goals. An evaluation procedure was conducted to validate the interview guide. Three research specialists thoroughly reviewed the interview questions. Following the validation, pilot interviews with a sample of randomly chosen people were carried out to check the clarity and accuracy of the interview guide's questions. The study used Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis for data interpretation following the data collection. In conducting this study, the researcher followed the ethical requirements and standards for qualitative research.

Data Analysis

The study used the thematic analysis developed by Virginia Braun and Victoria Clarke (2006, as cited in Caulfield, 2022). It involves the following steps: the first step is to get familiar with the data. A thorough overview of all the collected data is vital before analyzing individual items. The main procedure is transcribing audio, reading the text, taking initial notes, and looking through the data. The second step is to code the data. The researcher created codes after highlighting the important text sections of every transcript. The codes were then collated into groups, giving an overview of the main points and common meanings that recur throughout the data. The third step is to generate themes. The researcher reviewed codes, identify patterns, and create themes. Several codes were combined to create a single theme. The researcher discarded all irrelevant codes. The fourth step is reviewing themes. The researcher ensured that the themes are helpful and accurate by thoroughly checking all generated themes; otherwise, revisions will be made. The fifth step is to define and name the themes. The final list of themes was formulated precisely as to their meaning to represent the data. The themes were crafted as concise and understandable. The final step is writing up. The researcher established the findings based on the generated themes from the participants' experiences. The themes were discussed thoroughly with support from the theories viewed in this study and relevant studies.

Ethical Considerations

While doing qualitative research, ethical issues, such as anonymity, confidentiality, and informed consent, need to address, according to Sanjari et al. (2014) and Ignacio (2023). This study created standard guidelines to follow.

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Anonymity

This research protects the participants' identities. Anonymity was cited as a crucial component of data collection in qualitative research by Saunders et al. (2015). The participants are protected from concerns that could reveal their identities.

Confidentiality

The objective of confidentiality, like anonymity, is to safeguard the participants' identities. Tudy R. & Tudy I. (2016) assert that this was appropriate for maintaining anonymity and should be done to the fullest extent possible. Contextually, the study's conduct and the strictest secrecy for the participants' identifying information were observed.

Informed Consent

It is crucial to inform participants of the risks and benefits of participating in qualitative research as part of the informed consent process (Nusbaum et al., 2017). Before conducting the interviews, the participants were given informed consent that include the study's purpose, potential risks and benefits, and withdrawal rights. It indicated that the participants voluntarily agreed to participate actively in the study.

Rigors in Qualitative Research

The following qualitative research standards were followed to ensure this study's trustworthiness: credibility, confirmability, dependability, and transferability.

Credibility

According to Polit and Beck (2008), credibility refers to the accuracy of the information gleaned from participant viewpoints after careful interpretation and representation by the researcher. To ensure accuracy in this study, the data were translated carefully. Also, all themes were drawn out based only from the experiences of the participants.

Confirmability

Confirmability is all about having the results reflect what the participants said, not what the researcher thought (Cope, 2014; Polit & Beck, 2012; Tobin & Begley, 2004). In accordance to the methodology employed in the study, emergent themes were determined through rigorous analysis of all pertinent data following Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis. It maintained the authenticity and depth of the information derived from the participants' experiences.

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Dependability

Dependability speaks of the consistency of the data under comparable circumstances, which may be attained when other researchers or those planning to conduct studies similar to those already underway agree with the decision-making processes at each stage of the research process (Cope, 2014; Polit & Beck, 2012). The methodology of this study were explained precisely and discussed in factual details. Any replication of this study may be done.

Transferability

The adaptability of the research findings to various settings is what transferability is about (Houghton et al., 2013). The findings of the study were discussed in a way that other settings or fields could relate with. All drawn out themes and the discussions of the implications of the findings were simplified to ensure that they can be adapted to various settings.

RESULTS

This section presents the results coming from the interviews conducted to the participants of the study. It showcases various themes drawn out from the experiences of the participants specifically the psychosocial experiences they encountered and the sources of their mental health support.

Psychosocial Experiences encountered by First-Generation Working College Students

The study has drawn out six themes to describe the psychosocial experiences encountered by the participants.

Coping with Stress

The first theme that describes the psychosocial experiences of first-generation working college students is coping with stress. During the interviews they expressed that they feel under pressured and are overwhelmed with their obligations. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

Pressured sir, sobra jud ka ano sir, basta panganay man gud ka sir like murag tradition na gud diri sa Pilipinas sir na kailangan gud nimo hap-an gud tanan sir, pressured gud kaayo sir and kapoy, drainedkaayo. [P4]

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(I am pressured and it has been a tradition in the Philippines that as the eldest you need to work hard. I am pressured and exhausted.)

As a working student din po in regards with my personal life, uhm, medyo nakakaramdam ng pressure kasi parang yung mga responsibility ko sa school, sa pagtatrabaho, pati sa sarili ko medyo mahiraip i-manage kaya minsan parang nakakafeel din ng depression kasi hindi ko alam kung ano yung uunahin ko. [P6]

(As a working student, I feel pressure concerning my personal life because of the responsibilities at school, at work as well as with myself. I find it difficult to manage that is why sometimes I feel depressed because I do not know what to prioritize.)

Sa akong studies as panganay like lahi na gid akong murag mindset sir since nag-enter ko as working student kay murag lahi lahi na gud akong time sir. [P4]

(Regarding my studies, as the eldest, there is a different mindset since I entered as working student, my time is divided.)

Limited Socialization

The second theme concerns the limited socialization that first-generation working college students experience. During the interviews, they said they have no leisure time and have to prioritize their work and studies first. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

unfair siya for me sir kay hindi ko po maexperience yung mga naexperience ng ibang regular student kasi they have their leisure may extra time sila sa ganito ganyan [P1]

(It is unfair because I could not experience what regular students experience when they have their leisure and extra time.)

nung first year ako like before like meron kaming mga gala with friends may mga important kaming pupuntahan. But then, ngayon kay working student man ako kailangan ko muna yung, ay kailangan ko unahin yung work, kailangan ko unahin yung studies para lang, uhm para ma-sustain ko yung kailangan ng work and yung pag-aaral. [P2]

(In my first year, we went to important events before we bonded with friends. But then, now that I am a working student, I need to prioritize my work and studies to sustain the demands of my work and studies.)

May mga gatherings sir, ganyan hindi ako maka-attend agad kasi I have work po. [P5]

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(There are social gatherings which I could not attend to due to my work.)

Adjusting to Work Environment

The third theme that describes their psychosocial experiences is adjusting to the work environment. They mentioned during the interviews that they find it challenging to transition to work, blending with their colleague and workplace interactions. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

yung pag adjust ko sa environment since nagpasok ako na working student sir nung second semester nung second year, regular ako nung first year whole semester at saka first semester nung second year parang bago pa loang po sakin ang lahat and yung adjustment ko sir is yang slow paced po sir is because may times na parang hindi gud ako comfortable ko kasi iba yung environment ko before sa environment ko ngayon [P1]

(I was a regular student during the first year whole semester and the second year first semester. I became a working student during the second semester of second year. Everything is new to me, and the adjustment is slow-paced because there are times that I am uncomfortable with my new environment as compared to before.)

sa work environment syempre hindi na rin maiwasan na uhm meron talaga tayong mga colleagues no, or mga kasama sa trabaho na iba iba man tayo ng, like hindi na magkasang-ayon ba so I had to parang deal with it, kailangan ko makisabay sa ganon kasi kailangan. [P2]

(In a work environment, you cannot avoid having conflicts with your colleagues. So, I had to deal with and need to blend with them.)

sa mga challenges, uhm ano sir sa sarili sir. Sa aking sarili sir, I'm not sociable so for me challenging siya. siguro adjustment sa environment tapos, for me it's difficult po kasi sir na mag, kasi first time ko mag working [P3]

(I am not sociable. So for me, it is challenging. I also have to adjust to my environment. For me, it is difficult because it is my first time becoming a working student.)

Managing Time Effectively

The fourth theme is about managing time effectively. The students shared their experiences of having difficulties in managing their time. They said it is challenging to multitask and allocate their time appropriately. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

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yung life ko as a working student is not literally the same as ginagawa ng mga normal students sir. Medyo marami kami kailangang i-manage like sa time. Medyo mahirap siya sir, kasi I should participate well in my, in my classes sir tapos at the same time kailangan hindi mapektuhan yung sa work sir. [P5]

(My life as a working student is different from normal students. I have to manage a lot of things like time. It is not easy because I have to participate in my classes, and at the same time, my work should not be compromised.)

Malaki po na adjustment, as in sobrang laki po talaga ng adjustments kasi po yung sa oras um, naki, kasi nagkaron po ng conflict sa oras ng trabaho ko. Kasi morning palang po nagta-trabaho nako dito, 6am naga-in na po ako. Tapos tanghali, mag-out na po ako ng tanghali tapos minsan ma-late na po ako don sa mga subject ko po napasukan pagka-1 kaya minsan po nakiki-usap na lang po ako sa teachers na pwede po ba sa hapon na lang ako, or pwede po ba online na lang po ako, ganon po yung ginagawa ko na paraan. [P7]

(There is a big adjustment in time. There are conflicts regarding my duty hours. In the morning, I have to work at 6 am. Then, in the afternoon, I will do time out. Sometimes, I am late for my subjects, so I talk to my teachers if possible. I will attend the classes late afternoon or online to find a way.)

Makauli nako sa balay sir mga 7 o'clock niya magreview ko mga 1 hour lang sir para makatulong ko sayo para maprepare akong mind. Then kung magstart ng exam sir is gamay lang akong masulod sa utok sir ba kay limited lang akong time magreview sa school. [P8]

(I go home at 7 o'clock then I review for one hour so I can still sleep to prepare my mind. If there is an examination, I only absorbed few ideas since I have limited time to review at school.)

Sa pag-balance naman po nng academic, work and myself po, more on time management din po talaga kasi yan sir kasi marami pong mga gawain sa school and mostly sa pagtra-trabaho din kaya yung time management po talaga yun talaga yung nakakatulong sakin po. [P6]

(Balancing academic, work and myself, requires time management because there are lot of things at school and mostly at work that is why time management really helped me a lot.)

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Facing Academic Difficulties

The fifth theme is facing academic difficulties. The students shared their experiences as they needed to cope with their school work and the burnout they suffer. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

paano lang po ako mag cope up sa school activities sa school na mga requirements kasi po bawal, yung parang hindi po kasi naming ma-neglect yung duty namin as working since yun po ang naga sustain ng study naming so partially priority po naming ang aming duty aside sa other school activities [P1]

(How do I cope with school activities and requirements if it is not allowed to neglect our duty as working since it sustains our studies? We have to prioritize our duty instead of school activities.)

when it comes sa pag nakatambak na yung mga, yung paperworks mga ganon like ma burnt out ka talaga kasi sabay sabay, yun. [P2]

(When it comes to piling up with paper works like, I experience burnout.)

Sa school lang, ambot sir murag stressed man gud sir ba. Pero sa akong situation karon sir ma-balance nako siya sir pero manglisod lang ko explain if paunsa nako siya gina balance [P4]

(In school, I get really stressed; however, in my situation right now, it is hard to explain how I manage to balance my school obligations.)

hindi gud ako maka cope totally sa, sa ano sa ibang classmate ko na tawag niyan na may ibang school activity na mas ahead, na nakagawa na sila ahead kaysa saakin since busy ako parang makaisip gud ako sir na “kaya pa ba” ganito ganyan kasi motivation ko din po sir sa education ko kasi po parang as time passed by gud sir kay tawag niyan parang bombarded ng mga school activities [P1]

(I can't totally cope with my classmates who can do their school activities ahead of time, since I am busy. I usually think if I can still do it because my motivation in school as time passed by like I am bombarded with school activities.)

Dealing with Family Issues

The sixth theme is dealing with family issues. The students shared their experiences about attending to their family concerns and handling family problems that concern them the most. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

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sa family meron din akong personal battle about it and I have to look back kasi marami kami sa family kailangan ko i-balance ang pagiging anak, ang pagiging kapatid and that. [P2]

(I also have my battles with my family. I have to look back because there are many of us in the family, and I have to balance my role as a daughter and sibling.)

Kay pag naa man gud mga problems sa balay like murag mag-act na lang ka sir na murag like nothing happens like kay syempre sa work sir, gawork mi five hours every day including ang Saturday and murag draining ra gud sir then pag-abot nimo sa balay like same ano gyapon sir, naa gyapon mga problems sir [P4]

(If there are problems at home, I have to act like nothing has happened. In my work, I have to render five hours daily, including Saturday. It is draining, especially when I get back home, as the same problems stay.)

Sources of Mental Health Support of First-Generation Working College Students

There are a total of five themes that described the sources of mental health support which were generated coming from the experiences of the participants.

Self-reliance

Self-reliance is the first theme under the mental health support of first-generation working college students. Students usually rely on themselves whenever they feel exhausted from their experiences. They must instill a positive mindset, introspection, mental conditioning, and contemplation. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

aside from meron talaga akong friend na makausap ko, sarili ko lang talaga yung parang maghelp sayo na para maging okay ka, ano lang, yang think positive be optimistic lang sa mga nangyayari and parang gina encourage lang ang self ko na everything fall into place, na maging okay din ito, hindi ito always ganon, Yun lang, ganon, be optimistic. [P2]

(Aside from having a friend to talk to, I can only rely on helping myself to feel okay. I have to think positively, being optimistic about what I am dealing with. I must encourage myself that everything will fall into place and be alright.)

murag akong sarili lang akong ginaturya sir. Naga-rant lang ko sa akong sarili sir. [P4]
(I have to talk to myself. I usually rant to myself.)

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gina-put ko na lang sa mind ko sir na sige lang, mga ganon sir, mga may mga ganon talaga na tao, like gina-change ko gud yung mindset ko sir na dapat hindi ako magstay sa ganyan na mindset sir [P5]

(I have to instill in my mind that it is okay that there are people like them, and I have to change my mindset not to think negatively about the situation.)

self reflection gina self reflection nako akong sarili then ginajudge pud nako akong sarili sir ug tapos di na jud ko magpadala sa mga negative thoughts sa mga tao sir [P8]

(I do self-reflection then I evaluate myself. Also, I encourage myself not to be persuaded by my negative thoughts about others.)

Family

The second theme for their mental health support is family. Students expressed during the interviews that their family became a wall they could lean on. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

I am very thankful no kasi meron akong support like family, friends na parang mga ma-lean on ng shoulders [P2]

(I am very thankful that I have support from my family and friends, whom I can lean on.)

sa akong mama lang sir ginashare nako akong thoughts akong mga problems sa akong mother. Kay comfortable ko sa akong mother sir magshare ug mga problems nako sir [P8]

(I share my thoughts and my problems with my mother. It is because I am comfortable with her to share my problems.)

If ang problem nako sir is dili na gyud makaya sir, hard problem na gyud na sir, uhm ginashare na jud nako na sa akong parents sir, sa akong papa, sa akong mama ishare na gyud nako ni akong problems. [P8]

(If the problem is difficult to handle, I share it to my parents, to my father and my mother, I will share to them my problems.)

Friends

The third theme for their mental health support is through their friends. Students said that their friends help them cope with their problems. They can also open up about their feelings and gain wisdom from them. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

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I usually po talk to my friends yang parang magshare ako ng problems sa kanila na ginasabi ko din po na okay lang wala akong makuha na comments or suggestions from them as long as they listen po. And for me, talking to friends or someone na valuable to me po sir helps me to lessen or lose overwhelming emotions yung parang, parang tawag niyab anxiety ko gud sir na mag overthink ganito ganyan maglessen siya [P1]

(I usually talk to my friends to share my problems with them even if I cannot get their comments or suggestions as long as they listen. And for me, talking to friends or someone valuable helps me lessen or lose the overwhelming emotions like anxiety and overthinking.)

talking to my friends po. Kasi yung mga friends ko sa school is may mga problema ding dinadaan. And once na nakapag-open po ako sa kanila medyo gumagaan din po yung pakiramdam ko [P6]

(I talk to my friends at school whenever I am dealing with problems. And once I can open up to them at some point, it helps lessen my feelings.)

Kasi meron po akong kaibigan n active po talaga sa church, kasi minsan lang po talaga ako to be honest, honestly speaking minsan lang po ako nagasimba kasi sobrang busy po talaga. Uhm, siya po mismo nakipag-usap siya sakin, binibigyan niya ako ng mga words of wisdom [P7]

(I have a friend who is active in church. I rarely go to church because I am very busy. My friends usually approach me to give me words of wisdom.)

Once na nag-open ka sa friends mo, binigay mo yung mga, nilabas mo yung mga problema mo, parang nababawasan yung bigat na nararamdaman mo and helpful din siya sa health lifestyle mo. [P6]

(Once you open up to your friends, you are able to express your problems. It lessen the heavy feelings and it is helpful to your health lifestyle.)

Guidance from Professionals

The fourth theme regarding their mental health support is guidance from professionals. Students expressed during the interviews that they talk to their guidance counselors and reach out to their teachers whenever they have personal concerns. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

mga guidance counselors like something na makausap ko ba, like na makapaslabas sa ang aking feelings, like emotions, pagka-overwhelm, like happy like ganon at least maging okay lang ako. [P2]

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(The guidance counselors, like someone I can talk to, release my pent-up emotions and overwhelming experiences for me to be okay.)

nag-approach ako sa isa sa, ang teacher doon, sir then sinabi ko yung concern ko sir, then nag-open up ako sa kanya sir, then ayun po sir nag-advise siya na lapitan niya daw yung teacher na yun, sabihan niya din talk about sa situation ko then ayun sir. [P5]

(I approached one of my teachers, and then I shared my concerns. I opened up to her. Then, she gave me advice on what to do and will also talk to the other teacher about my situation.)

Learning from books

The fifth theme that describes their mental health support is learning from books. Students said that studying the Bible and browsing books help to feel at ease. These are evident in the succeeding interview extracts:

yung pagstu-study ng bible kasi isa din po yun sa nakakapag-relief sa akin and nakakababa din po ano, ng pressure, nawawala po yung pressure na nararamdaman ko po. [P6]

(Studying the Bible. It is one way for me to feel relief, and it lessens my pressure.)

para malaman nako ang self improvement diary sir through reading books kana sir the nagapangita ko ug mga strategies sa mga book kung papano manhandle ang mga ani na stiaution sir [P8]

(To improve myself, I read books and then find strategies from the books on how to handle various situations.)

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DISCUSSIONS

Discussions

This study explored the psychosocial experiences encountered by first-generation working college students and their sources of mental health support. Eight participants who met the criteria set by the study were interviewed. Their responses were analyzed using Braun and Clarke's thematic analysis. A total of six themes described their psychosocial experiences, and five themes for their mental health support.

Encountered Psychosocial Experiences of First-Generation Working College Students

As first-generation working college students, they encounter various psychosocial experiences. These experiences are described through the succeeding themes.

Coping with stress. One of the psychosocial experiences they encounter is coping with stress. They expressed during the interviews that they feel under pressure as they enter college. This pressure is due to their status, as they are the first members of their family to enter college. Several studies have identified how academic pressure affects first-generation college students (Covarrubias et al., 2020; Mangan, 2015; Sims & Ferrare, 2021; Tate et al., 2015). The pressure they are feeling concerns them the most. This pressure could affect their mental state as they achieve their educational aspirations.

Also, they acknowledged that they are overwhelmed with their obligations both at work and school. Rockman (2021), Tumin et al. (2020), and Zhang (2019) stated in their studies that working students have to juggle numerous responsibilities in work, academic, and personal lives to the point that it becomes a challenge for them to overcome. This situation makes their lives even harder. They have to attend and cope with these overwhelming obligations to achieve their goals.

Limited socialization. Another psychosocial experience they encounter is the limited socialization. They described during interviews that they no longer have leisure time. Acaso et al. (2019) and Wang et al. (2011) described that students who work while studying lack time to attend social gatherings because they have to maximize their time to render their duties in their work assignments. This depicts how their status as working students limits their daily activities and even attendance at social gatherings.

Further, they have to prioritize their work and studies over socializing with others. Since working students need to render services to sustain their studies, they need help socializing with others, unlike the regular students. They can no longer enjoy bonding with their friends

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because of their priorities (Bagabaldo et al., 2015; Finlay et al., 2012). It is hard for them to catch up with their friends because they have to perform multiple roles, which consumes most of their time and leaves them no free time for themselves and their significant others. These priorities limit their socialization.

Adjusting to work environment. In addition to the psychosocial experience they encounter, they are adjusting to the work environment. They expressed that transitioning to work is an overwhelming experience for them. According to Coral (2020) and Chang et al. (2020), many students transitioned from regular to working students because of their financial capacity to support their studies. Thus, transitioning to work as part of adjusting to their work environment seems inevitable for them.

Moreover, part of their adjusting to the work environment is blending with their colleagues. Several studies indicated that working students need help interacting with their colleagues due to their status as working students (De Kock, 2019; Logsdon, 2020; Pregoner et al., 2020). They need to adapt to various aspects of work, such as attending to their work schedules, performing their work obligations, and bonding with their colleagues. Adjusting to the work environment is necessary for working students to create harmonious relationships with the people at work and establish an engaging and positive workplace.

Managing Time Effectively. Also, managing time effectively is part of their psychosocial experiences. During the interviews, they indicated that it is a challenge for them to do multitasking. Several studies determined how difficult it is for working students to perform multiple roles (Coral, 2020; Pedroso et al., 2022; Rockman, 2021; Tumin et al., 2020; Zhang, 2019). They have to carry out their responsibilities as a student, worker, and family member.

In order to manage their time effectively, they have to allocate it, which is an essential skill they need to possess. As working students, they have to balance their roles properly. However, it is not easy for them to do so because of too many obligations they have to deal with (Logsdon, 2020; Mariano et al., 2022; Wang et al., 2011). To solve this, time management is one key factor that helps them perform their functions.

Facing Academic Difficulties. Further, facing academic difficulties is a typical scenario that they encounter. Performing multiple roles exhausts them the most. They have to cope with their obligations not only in work but also in their studies. Several studies indicated that working students face academic difficulties, risking their quality of life (Coral, 2020; Paje, 2023; Payusan et al., 2022; Tumin et al., 2020). They have to develop skills that allow them to cope with their academic concerns. Although they are working individuals, they are still students with educational aspirations.

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A part of these academic difficulties is the burnout they experience. This becomes a phenomenon among them because they must simultaneously juggle work, academics, and personal demands (Aspelmeier et al., 2012; Casamorin et al., 2023; Okado et al., 2021). This situation is crucial since they have to value the work that sustains their studies; however, they must maintain their studies, which they have to finish, and the sole reason they became working students.

Dealing with family issues. Lastly, as one of their psychosocial experiences, they have to deal with their family issues. As expressed during the interviews, they have to handle their family's problems while minding their obligations at work and school. These family problems could affect their academic performance, as stated in Al-Qudah & Hatahet (2016). That is why it is highly needed that they need to mitigate these issues so as not to compromise their academic standing.

Moreover, they have to attend to these concerns since there are prevailing issues they face. Being processed properly might positively influence their psychological makeup (Bennett, 2019; Deng et al., 2022). They usually bring with them the problems they have in their homes whenever they are at school or work, as much as they want to leave them behind. This completely bothers them, consciously or not, through their work or academic performances.

Sources of Mental Health Support of First-Generation Working College Students

The study identified various sources of mental health support of first-generation working college students. These include self-reliance, family, friends, guidance from professionals, and learning from books, which are discussed in the succeeding themes.

Self-reliance. The first mental health support that they have is through self-reliance. They usually maintain positive thinking at all times. The students must be optimistic regarding their situations, especially at work and school. Several studies have mentioned the importance of maintaining a positive outlook, especially for those who are working and studying at the same time (Ewen, 2023; Herzing University., 2021; Hess, 2023; Indeed Editorial Team., 2023; Yourtherapysource., 2019). Being positive helps manifest hope from their pressing issues.

Also, they must do self-talk to condition their mind to be okay when facing their challenges. Their ability to introspect gives them peace of mind, an important skill that students must possess alongside relying on themselves. This will help them stand on their feet during hard times (Mba, 2023; Nelson, 2021; Studio., 2020). To rely on oneself is a good mental health support because it is available in most cases.

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Family. The second mental health support they have is through their family. They described how they lean on their family to gain support from facing their problems. Atlas (2020) and Munguia (2019) stated how family support is crucial for students. The family can provide a good support system to which individuals could have direct access.

Further, whenever students experience downfall or are bombarded with so many negative emotions, they have their family with whom they can share their concerns. Family support is essential for working students because the support they gain from their families could help them overcome their psychological battles and facilitate academic success (De Andrade & Matias, 2017; Roksa & Kinsley, 2019). Since first-generation working college students are the first members of their families to enter college, support from their families is important because it could help them get motivated when their experiences are tough and overwhelming for them to handle.

Friends. They also have friends who serve as their mental health support. They talk with their friends when they feel they need someone to talk to about their problems at work, school, or personal. One (2021) and Reporter (2017) identified the importance of talking to friends, especially in college, where socialization is limited due to attending to multiple responsibilities. Engaging in communication with friends could help them maintain social interaction.

Further, opening up to friends is helpful as a means to protect mental health. Sharing their concerns with their friends is one technique to release their pent-up emotions whenever they are going through something. Studies have indicated the essence of having friends and how individuals can benefit from it (Cne, 2021; Lumugdan, 2022; Perna, 2010; Reporter, 2017). Friends maintain the social life among students to keep them sane from overwhelming experiences. As such, friends are one of the most accessible mental health supports because students find it comfortable to share their concerns with them.

Guidance from Professionals. Another mental health support they utilize is guidance from professionals. They expressed that they seek help from their school counselors whenever they have heavy feelings. Various studies described the importance of going to mental health professionals whenever someone experiences emotional distress (Abrams, 2022; Bauer, 2022; Vidourek et al., 2014). Guidance counselors are situated in every school to listen to students' concerns and help them adjust to their problems (Lee et al., 2021; Oswald et al., 2020; Lattie et al., 2019). The role of counselors in the school sometimes needs to be more appreciated. Also, utilizing their service is essential for students to safeguard their mental state.

Not only do they seek help from guidance counselors, but also from their teachers. Teachers' role in supporting students' mental health is vital because they are closer to students

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and know what is happening inside the classroom. As such, they are the referral sources who must work with school counselors to effectively help empower students' mental health (Korbey, 2022). Like guidance counselors, teachers are important figures for students because they learn and receive guidance from them.

Learning from books. Lastly, they read books to gain learning and insights. This mental health support allows them to discuss their inner thoughts by studying the Bible, for instance. If they have negative thoughts, they usually study the Bible to improve their mindset and attitude toward their situations. Both Diffey (2019) and Myers (2019) indicated that reading the bible could help college students put their minds at ease and improve their spirituality.

Also, part of learning from books is by reading self-help books. It helps them enhance their strengths and improve their weaknesses. It could boost their self-esteem and self-worth (Christian, 2023; Makhlof, 2022; mindbodygreen., 2022). Reading books allows them to gain learning and insights about life. It makes them interpret their experiences more positively.

Implication of Findings

First-generation working college students find living extremely difficult because they are the first in their families to attend college and must work to support their pursuit of higher education. Their capacity to successfully manage their time worries them the most. They are forced to make many sacrifices and go through various experiences, including missing out on social interactions with friends, being unable to participate in school events actively, submitting work late, dealing with personal battles, and managing the pressures of life. As they commonly said during the interviews, they feel "unfair" because they cannot do what regular students enjoy.

Moreover, the sources of their mental health support keep them sane from their overwhelming experiences. Fortunately, the students know how to seek help when battling personal issues affecting their work and studies. They have identified multiple sources they run to and lean on when they need a rescue. As such, this support exists because of their challenging experiences, which are indispensable given the nature of their lives as first-generation working college students.

Conclusion

First-generation working college students encounter various psychosocial experiences. These include the stress they cope with from work, academics, and personal, the limited socialization they have because they have to set their priorities, the need to adjust to their work environment, how they can manage their time effectively so they can perform their roles and responsibilities, the academic difficulties they are facing, and the family issues

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they are dealing. Therefore, these psychosocial experiences are essential to explore to gain insights that will be the benchmark for creating intervention programs. This could help the students achieve their education goals while performing their huge responsibilities in school, work, and home.

Further, they have numerous sources for their mental health support. These include their reliance on themselves, the support they receive from their families, the help they get from their friends, the guidance from professionals, and the learning they acquire from books. Thus, their ability to possess help-seeking behaviors is commendable. What they are going through takes work to handle. These sources of mental health support allow them to see their lives in a better way despite the hardships they experience. These will safeguard their well-being as they proceed to the journeys of their lives.

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